

A PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF A PSYCHOSOMATIC PHRASEOLOGICAL UNIT IN THE TURKIC LANGUAGES: EVIDENCE FROM MODERN TURKISH AND AZERBAIJANI

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Abstract: *The psycholinguistic analysis of psychosomatic phraseologisms in the Turkic languages reveals that these expressions possess a highly multifaceted component structure and in most cases, exhibit a universal character. However, even in such cases, this componential variation does not obscure the universal nature of the semantic load conveyed. This is because psychosomatic phraseologisms arise directly from the figurative characterization of a person's psycho-emotional state or are used to evaluate psychosomatic conditions in other contexts.*

Keywords: *psychosomatics, phraseologisms, psycholinguistics, modern Turkish, Azerbaijani*

Annotatsiya: *Turk tillaridagi psixosomatik frazeologizmlarning psixolingvistik tahlili ushbu birliklarning murakkab va ko'p qirrali komponent tuzilishga ega ekanini hamda aksariyat hollarda universal xarakter kasb etishini ko'rsatadi. Biroq, komponentlar tarkibinda müşahidə olunan bu cür variativlik ifadə olunan semantik yukning universal mahiyyətini kölgada qoldirmaydi. Chunki psixosomatik frazeologizmlar bevosita insonning psixo-emotsional holatini obrazli tarzda xarakterlash asosida yuzaga keladi yoki boshqa kontekstlarda psixosomatik holatlarni baholash üçün qo'llaniladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *psixosomatika, frazeologizmlar, psixolingvistika, zamonaviy turk tili, ozarbayjon tili.*

Аннотация: *Психолингвистический анализ психосоматических фразеологизмов в тюркских языках показывает, что данные выражения обладают сложной и многоаспектной компонентной структурой и в большинстве случаев носят универсальный характер. Однако даже при наличии компонентной вариативности универсальность передаваемой семантической нагрузки не утрачивается. Это объясняется тем, что психосоматические фразеологизмы формируются на основе образной характеристики психоэмоционального состояния человека либо используются для оценки психосоматических состояний в иных контекстах.*

Ключевые слова: *психосоматика, фразеологизмы, психолингвистика, современный турецкий язык, азербайджанский язык.*

It is well known that the phraseological system of a language is rich in expressions related to human psycho-emotional states, reflecting various emotional experiences and psychosomatic reactions. The manifestation of semantic universality in psychosomatic phraseologisms [6, pp. 46–53] provides grounds for asserting that human beings tend to express their psychological and emotional states – as well as the physiological discomfort

experienced during illness or distress – through eloquent, metaphorical language. While certain linguocultural determinants undoubtedly play a role [11, pp. 12–16], the predominance of common features leaves little room for doubt regarding their universality (for a more detailed discussion, see [12, pp. 114–117]).

One of the aspects that makes this group of phraseological units particularly interesting from a research perspective is their broad and diverse componential composition, encompassing somatic, zoometaphoric, and phytometaphoric elements, among others. For instance:

“*qurd kimi ac olmaq / kurt gibi aç olmak*” (“to be hungry like a wolf”),

“*özünü quş kimi hiss etmək / kuş gibi hissetmek*” (“to feel as light as a bird”),

“*ürəyi quş kimi çırpınmaq*” (“one’s heart flutters like a bird”),

“*qarnı qurdlu olmaq*” (“to have worms in the stomach”),

“*ürəyini qurd yemək / içini kurt kemirmək*” (“to be gnawed by anxiety,” literally “for one’s heart/inside to be eaten by a worm”) – all examples with zoomorphic components [9, pp. 762, 539, 771];

or “*nanə yarpağı kimi əsmək / payız yarpağı kimi əsmək*” (“to tremble like a mint leaf / autumn leaf”) – with phytometaphoric components [9; pp. 604, 663], among others.

As noted in the collaborative research of A. Silha, A. Saldanha, and their colleagues, psychosomatic expressions manifested in language frequently represent the verbalization of psychoanalytic processes [7, 1–2]. In other words, psychosomatically conditioned expressions, by their functional nature, embody an individual’s (or another person’s) awareness of psycho-emotional tension and possess the capacity to articulate both its causes and its external manifestations.

For example, in contemporary Turkish, the expressions *yumşak karınlı olmak* or *yumşak karnı olmak* (“to have a soft belly”) are commonly employed to denote a person’s weak spot, their vulnerable, fragile, or defenseless aspect [10]. This expression is directly conditioned by a psychosomatic correlation, referring to the physiological reality that the soft abdominal tissues constitute a bodily area that is particularly sensitive and unprotected against external impact. The following examples illustrate this usage: “*İrak’ın yumuşak karnını fırsata çevirmede en başarılı ülke: İran*” (“Iran is the country that has most successfully turned Iraq’s soft belly into an opportunity”) [8]; “*Seçimli otokrasilerin yumuşak karnını doğal olarak seçim kazanma gereği oluşturuyor*” (“The need to win elections naturally constitutes the soft belly of electoral autocracies”) [4].

As the examples demonstrate, the semantic content of this expression corresponds to that of the universally recognized idiom *Achilles’ heel* (*Axilles dabanı // Axillesin dabanı // Aşil’in topuğu*), which belongs to the category of phraseological units grounded in universal background knowledge. Consider, for instance, the following: “*Aşilin topuğu insanların mutlaka bir zaaflarının olacağına işaret eder*” (“The Achilles’ heel points to the fact that every person inevitably possesses a weakness”) [3]; “When referring to a person’s weak point, the expression *Achilles’ heel* is used” [2]. Given that this expression has found its way into the phraseological dictionary of the language [9, p. 72] and has been included in linguistic analyses [1; pp. 9–10], its establishment as a psychosomatically conditioned expression of universal character becomes even more evident.

This expression, grounded in a historically and socially determined vertical context and containing an anthroponymic-mythonymic component, is also productive in Turkish

and conveys a comparable semantic value. However, while *Achilles' heel* derives from Greek mythology and Homer's *Iliad*, the idiom *yumuşak karın* is rooted exclusively in psychosomatic conceptualization, yet it conveys an analogous meaning: “*İslam geleneğinde kadın, tabirin tam anlamıyla bir 'yumuşak karın'dır*” (“In the Islamic tradition, woman is, in the full sense of the term, a ‘soft belly’”) [5].

Evidently, in this case, we observe the verbal representation of a mental gestalt or psycho-emotional taboo through the expression *yumuşak karın*. The author, who rejects accusations concerning the excessively patriarchal nature of attitudes toward women in Islam, employs this psychosomatic idiom in a rhetorically charged manner to underscore that the theme of womanhood constitutes one of the most delicate, vulnerable, and consequently most disputable and interpretatively open issues within this religious system.

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